

WRC-23 Outcome

**Updates from the Decisions of World Radio Conference 2023
Dubai November 13 to December 19, 2023**

[10.5281/zenodo.13994378](https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.13994378)

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ITU - World Radio Conferences

- It is job of WRC to review, and, if necessary, revise the Radio Regulations, the international treaty governing the use of the radio-frequency spectrum and satellite orbits
- WRC is held every 3 to 4 years. Each study cycle initiates just after the WRC

High level process landscape diagram:

Next RAWRC will be held in Dubai: RA-23 (Dubai, 13-17 Nov. 2023); WRC-23 (Dubai, 20 Nov.-15 Dec. 2023)

WRC Process

✓ WRC-23 was held in UAE-Dubai from 13 Nov. to 19 Dec. 2023

RA-23 (Dubai, 13-17 Nov. 2023);
WRC-23 (Dubai, 20 Nov.-15 Dec. 2023);

CPM-27-1 (Dubai, 18 -19 Dec. 2023)

Simultaneous work in six languages -
English, French, Arabic, Chinese,
Russian, and Spanish

4500 participants

22% women participants (up 4% from
Previous conference in 2019)

WRC-23 had 19 specific agenda items and 6 standing Agenda items (2,4,7,8,9,10)

Chapter of CPM Report	Assigned Agenda Items
WP1: Fixed, Mobile and Broadcasting Issues	1.1, 1.2, 1.3, 1.4,1.5, 9.1 (c), RR 21.5 (Doc.550)
WP2: Aeronautical and Maritime Issues	1.6, 1.7, 1.8, 1.9, 1.10, 1.11 Res.427
WP3: Science Issues	1.12, 1.13, 1.14, 9.1 a) , d) and WRC-19 Doc.573
WP4: Satellite Issues	1.15, 1.16, 1.17, 1.18, 1.19 & 7
WP5: General Issues	2, 4, 8, 9.1 b), and 10

WRC-23 recognized that Wireless Communications Services will continue to need more and more spectrum

Band (MHz)	600-960 MHz	1.4 GHz, 2GHz, 2.5 GHz	3-4 GHz	4.4 - 6 GHz	6-15.35 GHz	26 GHz	40,50, 60 GHz
4G/5G	700, 800, 900 MHz	1700-2690 MHz	3300-3700 MHz	4.4 - 4.95 GHz		26 GHz	40 GHz
6G	600-960 MHz	1700-2690 MHz	3300-3700 MHz	4.4- 4.8 GHz	7-8 GHz 14.8-15.35 GHz	26 GHz	40. 50, 60 GHz
Wi-Fi		2.4 GHz		5 GHz	6 GHz		60-70 GHz (V band)

WRC-23 decided to open many new frequency bands for 4G/5G/6G

- ✓ WRC-23 identified new frequency bands for International Mobile Telecommunications (IMT), which will be crucial for expanding broadband connectivity and mobile services in various countries and regions. (IMT is the ITU word for 4G, 5G and, in the future, 6G communications)

3 300-3 400 MHz	4 800-4 990 MHz (with power limits)
3 600-3 800 MHz	6 425-7 125 MHz (in Region 1)

- ✓ The WRC also recognised the use of 6425 to 7125 MHz for wireless access and RLANS in the Radio Regulation table of frequency allocations for the first time.
- ✓ These are in addition to the 5 new bands that were identified for 5G in mm wave bands above 24 GHz at WRC-19:
 - ✓ 24.25-27.5 GHz (26 GHz), 37-43.5 GHz (40 GHz), 45.5-47 GHz & 47.2-48.2 (50 GHz) and 66-71 GHz for IMT (70 GHz)

WRC-23 also opened many frequency bands for IMT base stations based on High Altitude Platforms

- ✓ WRC-23 also identified a number of IMT bands below 2.7 GHz for use of high-altitude platform stations for IMT base stations (HIBS) and established regulations for their operations. It offers a new platform to provide mobile broadband using the same frequencies and devices as IMT mobile networks. HIBS can contribute to bridging the digital divide in remote and rural areas and maintain connectivity during disasters.

WRC-23 directed new studies to consider many new frequency bands for 6G at WRC-27

- ✓ WRC-23 also approved new studies for identification of IMT for 4G, 5G and 6G at WRC-27 in
 - ❖ 4.4-4.8 GHz,
 - ❖ 7-8 GHz and
 - ❖ 14.8-15.35 GHz
- ✓ These studies will target for additional 2 GHz mid band spectrum for IMT at WRC-27 in time for rollout of 6G technologies
- ✓ WRC-23 also approved new studies for satellites to have direct connectivity with mobile phones in UHF bands between 700 MHz and 2700 MHz. These studies will lead to use of NGSO satellites to connect directly with ground based mobile terminals using IMT technology

WRC-23 decisions on Satellites support ubiquitous connectivity

including increased spectrum access for mobile connectivity on sea, air and ground

- ✓ WRC-23 permitted NGSO Earth Stations in Motion (ESIMs) to use new frequencies to deliver high-speed broadband on-board aircraft, vessels, trains, and vehicles. These satellite services are also critical during disasters where local communication infrastructure is damaged or destroyed.
- ✓ WRC-23 took regulatory actions including the implementation of e-navigation systems to enhance distress and safety communications at sea to support the modernization of the Global Maritime Distress and Safety System (GMDSS)
- ✓ WRC-23 also laid down spectrum rules for direct wireless and optical connections between NGSO satellites
- ✓ WRC-23 also streamlined the rules for NGSO satellites to maintain their stations within prescribed limits

WRC-23 decisions on Satellites support ubiquitous connectivity

including increased spectrum access for mobile connectivity on sea, air and ground

- ✓ **WRC-23 decided to protect ship and aircraft mobile service stations located in international airspace and waters from other stations within national territories. WRC-23 also allocated new frequencies to the aviation industry for aeronautical mobile satellite services (117.975-137 MHz).**
- ✓ **WRC-23 agreed to allocate additional frequencies for passive Earth exploration satellite services to enable advanced ice cloud measurements for better weather forecasting and climate monitoring.**
- ✓ **WRC-23 agreed for the importance of space weather observation to recognize the operation of space weather sensors as part of the meteorological aid service to observe space weather phenomena including solar flares, solar radiation and geomagnetic storms which can interfere with radio- communication services including satellites, mobile phone services and navigation systems.**

THANK
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